

Interview on the development of SNOPI

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*Obrigatório

Participant Profile

PP1. Name *

Sua resposta

PP2. Position currently held *

Sua resposta

PP3. Highest academic degree *

- Elementary school
- High school
- Bachelor's degree

PP4. Status of the highest academic degree *

- Complete
- Incomplete

PP5. Inform the course or area with the highest degree *

Computer Science

Information Systems

Computer Engineering

Outro: _____

PP6. Theoretical and practical knowledge in systems development, ontologies and development of systems based on ontologies: *

	None	Low (did not take any courses or discipline and gained some knowledge by reading books or other materials)	Medium (did a course or training on the subject, with a minimum duration of 4 hours or worked with the subject in an Initiation or Graduation Project or in small projects in a company)	High (expert in the subject, have some certification in the area or have worked with the subject in master's or doctoral research or in a company)
Systems development (theoretical)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Systems development (practical)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ontology (theoretical)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ontology (practical)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Development of based systems in ontologies (theoretical)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Development of based systems in ontologies (practical)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Voltar

Enviar

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